

**A REVIEW STUDY ON VRANASHOPHA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO EARLY
STAGE CELLULITIS*****¹Dr. Omkar A. Kadam, ²Dr. R. C. Yakkundi, ³Dr. Anju D. R.**¹1st Year Year PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalya Tantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.²Professor and HOD Dept. of Shalya Tantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.³Assistant Professor, Dept. of Shalya Tantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Omkar A. Kadam**1st Year Year PG Scholar, Dept. of Shalya Tantra, SSRAMC, Inchal, Belagavi.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18428237>**How to cite this Article:** *¹Dr. Omkar A. Kadam, ²Dr. R. C. Yakkundi, ³Dr. Anju D. R. (2026). A Review Study On Vranashopha With Special Reference To Early Stage Cellulitis. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(2), 26–28.

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ABSTRACT

Vranashopha is the most encountered condition in *Shalyatantra* which has to be treated as early as possible to avoid further surgical intervention and complication. The definition of *Shopha* given by *Acharya Sushruta* is a localized swelling in part of the body involving *Twak* and *Mamsa Dhatu* which may be even or uneven, massive and knotty in consistency.^[1] It is the prodromal stage of *Vrana*. The *Samanya Lakshana* are *Gaurava* (Heaviness), *Anavasthitva* (Mobile), *Utsedha* (Swelling), *Ushama* (Heat), *Siratanutva* (Increases vascular permeability), *Romaharsha* (Horripilation) and *Vivarnata* (Discoloration).^[2] These organisms usually gain access through a wound or scratch or insect bite. The organisms on skin and its appendages gain entrance to dermis and multiply to cause Cellulitis.^[3]

KEYWORDS: *Vranashopha*, Cellulitis, *Ayurveda*.**INTRODUCTION**

Vranashopha is considered an early sign or the initial stage in the formation of *Vrana* (wound).^[4] *Acharya Sushruta* has described *Vranashopha* based on the vitiation of *Doshas* and explained its characteristics depending on the predominance of each *Dosha*.^[5] This condition progresses through three distinct stages: *Amaavastha* (the initial phase of inflammation), *Pachyamanavastha* (the stage of active inflammation), and *Pakwavastha* (the suppurative stage).^[6]

Vranashopha is defined as a localized swelling involving the *Twak* (skin) and *Mamsa* (muscles), which may appear either even or uneven due to the accumulation of vitiated *Doshas* in a specific area of the body. If not treated promptly, it can eventually develop into *Vrana* (ulcer or wound).^[7] The description of *Shopha* by *Sushruta* closely correlates with the concept of inflammatory swelling in modern medicine. Contemporary science defines inflammation by the classical signs: *Rubor* (redness), *Calor* (heat), *Tumor* (swelling), *Dolor* (pain), and *Functinolaesa* (loss of function).^[8] Clinically, such inflammatory conditions can

present as boils, furunculosis, cellulitis, erysipelas, and similar disorders. Suppurative inflammatory swellings are comparable to the Ayurvedic concept of *Vranashopha*.

Acharya Sushruta further classified *Vranashopha* into six types based on the predominant *Dosha*: *Vataja*, *Pittaja*, *Kaphaja*, *Raktaja*, *Sannipataja*, and *Agantuja*.^[9] The diagnosis and differentiation of *Vranashopha* are made by observing features such as its color, severity of pain, and texture on palpation.^[10] The incidence rate of cellulitis is reported as 24.6 cases per 1,000 person-years, with higher prevalence among males and individuals aged 45–64 years.^[11]

Management of cellulitis in modern medicine typically involves antibiotics, analgesics, and anti-inflammatory agents. However, the prolonged use of antibiotics is often associated with adverse effects, and the overall treatment can become financially burdensome due to the high cost of medications and hospital stays.

In Ayurveda, the treatment of *Vranashotha* includes seven specialized therapeutic approaches: *Vimlapana* (fomentation and massage), *Avasechana* (bloodletting), *Upanaha* (application of poultice), *Patana* (surgical intervention), *Shodhana* (cleansing of the wound), *Ropana* (healing measures), and *Vaikrutapaha* (removal of scar deformities).^[12] The first two methods are especially recommended during the *Amaavastha* stage to prevent further progression of the condition, while the remaining procedures are implemented in the subsequent stages.^[13]

Acharya Sushruta has elaborated on *Sapta Upakrama* (seven therapeutic measures), *Ekadasha Upakrama* (eleven therapeutic measures), and *Shashti Upakrama* (sixty therapeutic measures)^[14] for the effective management of *Vranashotha* and *Vrana*.

Types of Vrana Shopha

1. *Vataja*
2. *Pittaja*
3. *Kaphaja*
4. *Sannipataka*
5. *Raktaja*
6. *Agantuja*

STAGES OF VRANA SHOPHA

There are 3 stages of Vrana Shopha.

1] Aamawastha

This is a Stage of unripe abscess (early inflammation) of vrana. This stage formed due to vitiated Doshas and Dushyas, in this stage Kapha Dosha aggravated due to which a swelling was produced. Feeling of cold/hot, induration, dull pain, mild inflammation etc.

2] Pachyamanawastha - Stage of ripening abscess (inflammatory stage)

The vitiated Doshas are further allowed to produced more exaggerated phase in which the Prakupita Pitta dosha will acts on the Dushya and this stage produced symptoms like as Pricking and other types of pain, Discolouration of skin, burning sensation, Pyrexia etc.

3] Pakwawastha: Stage of riped abscess (suppuration)

In this stage there is Dosha Dushya Sammurchana the Dhatus are affected and burnt. There is *shoshana* of *vrana shopha* by *Vata dosha* due to which following sign and symptoms was produced this results in decreases pain, pallor, etc.

Treatment of Vrana Shopha

Vrana Shopha Was managed by in early stages to avoid the suppuration. The management is required in different stages of Shopha like in Amawastha only Vimlapana, Alepa, Upanaha etc. are needed for treatment while in Pakwawastha, Bhedana etc. are needed for treatment. Acharya Sushruta has mentioned 7 Treatment of *Vrana Shopha*.

- **Vimlapana:** Light rubbing or massage over Vranashopha (to improve circulation)
- **Avasechana:** Elimination therapy including blood letting (for removal of toxins)
- **Upahana:** Poultice (Application of Medicated paste).
- **Patana:** Operative procedure (I and D).
- **Shodhana:** Antiseptic measures (detoxification).
- **Ropana:** Healing measures
- **Vaikrutapaha:** To restore normalcy of scar

CONCLUSION

Vranashopha is one the major concern in Shalya, and it has been treated by humans since the civilization. The injury from many causes that caused the Vrana was the first thing the men came across under the conditions. Vrana is a terrible and inactivating condition that can afflict anyone of any age. The most important chapter of Shalya is Vrana, as successful Shalya tantra practitioner must possess the knowledge of effective management of Vrana.

REFERENCES

1. Shastri A.D., Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika commentary on Sushruta Samhita Sutrasthana: Chapter 17 verse 3. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, (Ed.), 2018; pg.91-92.
2. Sharma R.K, Dash Bhagawan, Charaka samhita English Translation, chikitsa sthana: chapter 12 verse 11, vol 3. Varanasi: Choukhamba Sanskrit series office, (Ed.), 2012; pg.485.
3. Bhat MS, SRB'S Manual of surgery, 5th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers medical publishers, 2016; pg.36-37.
4. Yadunandana U. Madhava Nidanam. 31st ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthana; 2002. Chap. 41, shloka 1.
5. Srikantha Murthy KR. Susruta Samhita, Vol 1. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2014; Sutrasthana, Chap. 17, shloka 4, p. 123.
6. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Nibandha Sangraha commentary by Dalhanacharya. Reprint ed. Yadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2003; p. 82. (Su. Su. 17/5).
7. Srikantha Murthy KR. Susruta Samhita, Vol 1. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2014; Sutrasthana, Chap. 17, shloka 3, p. 122.
8. Das S. A Manual on Clinical Surgery. 11th ed. Kolkata: S. Das, 2015; p. 41.
9. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Ayurved Tattva Sandipika by Ambikadatta Shastri. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthana, 2016; Sutrasthana, 17/4, p. 92.
10. Srikantha Murthy KR. Susruta Samhita, Vol 1. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2014; Sutrasthana, Chap. 17, shloka 4, p. 123.
11. Perelló-Alzamora M, García-Esteban C, López-Gómez S, et al. Cellulitis incidence in a defined population. ResearchGate. Available from:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7287353_Cellulitis_incidence_in_a_defined_population

12. Shastri KA. Sushruta Samhita edited with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika. Reprint ed. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2007; Sutrasthana, Chap. 17/18, p. 77.
13. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Nibandha Sangraha commentary by Dalhanacharya. Reprint ed. Yadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2003; p. 84. (Su. Su. 17/17).
14. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Nibandha Sangraha commentary by Dalhanacharya. Reprint ed. Yadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2003; p. 397. (Su. Chi. 1/7).
15. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Nibandha Sangraha commentary by Dalhanacharya. Reprint ed. Yadavaji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2003.